

Physico-Chemical Studies on the Composition and Stability of the Chelate Formed between Vanadium (V) and Alizarin Red S

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The composition of the red-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 470 m μ) between pentavalent vanadium and Alizarin Red S is reported to be 1:2. The chelate is stable in the pH range of 3.0 to 6.5. The value of log K at 25° (pH 3.5, $\mu=0.1M$) is 8.5 ± 0.2 and ΔG° at the same temperature is -11.7 ± 0.3 K cal./mole.

Banerji and Dey¹ reported that with Alizarin Red S vanadium (V) formed a stable red-coloured chelate. They established the composition of the chelate by the method of continued variations only, using absorbance data. In this communication, the composition of the chelate has further been confirmed by electrical conductance measurements using the methods of continued variations, the slope-ratio method of Harvey and Manning², and the mole-ratio method of Yoe and Jones³ using spectrophotometric measurements. Results of these methods indicate that a complex is formed by two molecules of the reagent with one of vanadium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of ammonium vanadate (B.D.H. -LR) and Alizarin Red S (B.D.H. indicator) were prepared in double distilled water, free from carbon dioxide, and were standardised by the usual methods. The absorbance of the solutions was measured with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, operated by a Doran's mains unit connected to 220 V /50 cycles a. c. mains, further stabilised by a constant voltage transformer. Electrical conductance measurements were made with a Leeds Northrup Kohlrausch slidewire with an audio-frequency oscillator in the circuit, operated on the same mains, using a dip type measuring cell having a cell constant of 0.580. The experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned room maintained at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The total volume of all the mixtures prepared for measurements was kept at 50 ml. The individual solutions and mixtures were kept immersed in a Townson and Mercer's Precision Thermostat, maintained at a temperature, of $25^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ for about 3 hours.

Hydrogen-ion concentrations of the solutions were measured with a Leeds and Northrup direct reading pH indicator, operated on the aforementioned mains. The electrode

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1961, **309**, 226.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4438.

3. *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

system was glass-calomel, supplied by the same manufacturer. *pH*s of the solutions and mixtures were adjusted to 3.5 ± 0.2 by addition of HCl or NaOH.

For the mole-ratio method, a series of solutions was prepared containing a constant amount of Alizarin Red S and increasing ratios of the metal to the reagent. The ionic strength of the solutions was adjusted to 0.1*M* by addition of sodium perchlorate. Absorbances of the solutions were measured against distilled water blanks at different wave lengths and were plotted against concentration ratios of the metal to the ligand.

The legends related to Figs. 1 and 2 have been shown in Table I.

Two series of solutions were prepared for the slope-ratio method. In the first series, varying amounts of ammonium vanadate were added to a constant excess of Alizarin Red S. The other series contained a constant excess of ammonium vanadate and varying concentrations of Alizarin Red S. Absorbance readings of the solutions were noted against a distilled water blank at different wave lengths.

For measurements involving electrical conductance, mixtures were prepared according to the continued variations method, the total volume being kept at 50 ml in each case.

The stability constant was calculated from the mole-ratio method through a calculation of the degree of dissociation.

If the dissociation of the complex be represented by

where c is the total concentration of the complex in moles per litre assuming no dissociation and α is the degree of dissociation, the dissociation constant may be written as

$$K_{\alpha} = \frac{(\alpha c) (n\alpha c)^n}{c(1-\alpha)}$$

The value of n for the complex having been established, value of α may be obtained from the mole-ratio curves by the relation :

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

E_m is the maximum extinction obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve indicating that all the reagent is present in the form of the complex. E_s is the extinction at the stoichiometry.

DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry of the Components

The following table summarises the observations involving conductometric measurements (Figs. 1 and 2) on the composition of the chelate by the method of continued variations. Here c indicates the concentration of the metal ion and $p = c'/c$, c' being the concentration of the chelating agent.

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	Peak occurring at volume of NH_4VO_3 .	Composition of the chelate V(V): ARS.
1	A	6.66M	1.00	16.7 ml	1:2
	B	5.00	1.00	16.7	1:2
	C	4.00	1.00	16.7	1:2
2	A	4.00	1.66	22.5	1:2
	B	5.00	1.33	20.0	1:2
	C	4.00	1.25	19.4	1:2

Table I shows that the ratio of vanadium to Alizarin Red S in the chelate is 1:2. Results obtained by the mole-ratio method (Figs. 3 and 4) and the slope-ratio method (Figs. 5 and 6) confirm this composition.

Figs. 3 and 4 represent determination of the composition from absorbance studies using the mole-ratio method; $p\text{H}=3.5 \pm 0.2$; $\mu=0.1$ (NaClO_4).

FIG. 3. Mole-ratio method at 480 $\text{m}\mu$.
 Curve A : Conc. of ARS = $3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 B : ,, ,, = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 4 Mole-ratio method at 470 $\text{m}\mu$.
 Curve A : Conc. same as in Fig. 3, A.
 B : Conc. same as in Fig. 3, B.

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration on the Stability of the Chelate

The absorbances of a number of mixtures containing NH_4VO_3 and Alizarin Red S in the ratio of 1:2 ($c = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $c' = 2.50 \times 10^{-4} M$) at different pH s were measured at various wave lengths and at the wave length of maximum absorbance of the chelate which was 470 $\text{m}\mu$ and remaining the same between pH 3.0 and 6.5, showing thereby that the stability of the chelate was in this range of pH .

Figs. 5 and 6 represent determination of the composition from absorbance studies using the slope-ratio method; $\text{pH} = 3.5 \pm 0.2$ at 470 $\text{m}\mu$ (upper curve) and at 480 $\text{m}\mu$ (lower curve).

FIG. 5

Conc. of excess component = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Conc. of variable component = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

FIG. 6

Excess component = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Variable component = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Calculation of the Stability Constant

Table II records the values of $\log K$ determined by the continued variations method and the mole-ratio method. The particular values of pH and ionic strength are also mentioned. The free energy change of formation has also been calculated with the help of the expression:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K,$$

the terms having their usual significance.

TABLE II

Method employed.	pH .	Ionic conc.	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (Kcal.).
Banerji and Dey	3.5 ± 0.2	0.1 M (NaClO_4)	8.6 ± 0.3	-11.8 ± 0.6^x
Mole ratio	3.5 ± 0.2	0.1 M (NaClO_4)	8.5 ± 0.2	-11.7 ± 0.3 (author)

It is clear from the above table that the values obtained by both the methods are in close agreement with each other.

Structure of the Chelate

According to Mukherji and Dey⁴, sodium alizarin 3-sulphonate undergoes variation in colour with change in hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium. Their observations, regarding the shift in λ_{max} of the reagent with change in pH of the solution are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

pH.	Region of maximum absorbance.
1.0—5.0	430 m μ
5.0—12.0	520
12.0 and above	560

From above, it is evident that there are at least three distinct regions of maximum absorbance and therefore it may be assumed that the reagent exists in three different forms depending on the hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium. Baghava Rao and co-workers⁵ represented the ionisation of Alizarin Red S molecule by the following structures:

The compound itself is weakly acidic in solution; in a more strongly acidic medium, the ionisation of the hydroxyl group is suppressed and the acid form develops structure (I) below pH 5.0. Structure (II) represents the half-neutralised stage and predominates when the medium has pH between 5.0 and 12.0, whereas in excess of alkali the molecule acquires structure (III).

Different views have been suggested regarding the position of the chelate ring in the structure of metal chelates with Alizarin Red S. The metal ion may be chelated either (i) between a pair of phenolic oxygens or (ii) between α phenolic oxygen and the adjacent quinoid oxygen.

The λ_{max} of the chelate is at 470 m μ . It seems therefore that the metal ion is chelated between two phenolic oxygens as shown below:

4. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 242.

5. *Anal.-Ohim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 142.

Similar structures have been suggested by Leibhafsky and Winslow⁶ in the case of zirconium and hafnium complexes and of lead and copper complexes by Mukherji and Dey.⁷ This would lead to the formation of an anionic complex. The anionic nature of the complex has been confirmed by the adsorption of the colour of the chelate by a bed of ion-exchange resin, Amberlite I R-45(OH).

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6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1176; 1947, **69**, 1130.

7. *This Journal*, 1957, **34**, 641.